

EUROPEANA Media

Document: Second Iteration Usability Evaluation Report

FINAL

ACTIVITY 3: USABILTY EVALUATION

**Produced under the Grant agreement No INEA/CEF/ICT/A2017/1564684 Europeana Media for
the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency
Department C – Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) – TELECOMMUNICATIONS SECTOR**

**This project is co-funded by
the European Union**

10 January 2020

Europeana Media

EUPS Second Iteration Usability Evaluation

Document: EUPS Second Iteration Usability Evaluation Final Version (10 January 2020)

Date of Delivery of Initial Version: 30 December 2019

Activity 3: Usability Evaluation

Authors: Abiodun Ogunyemi (TIB), Margret Plank (TIB)

Contributors: Mathy Vanbuel (ATiT), Marco Rendina (LUCE), all partners.

Reviewers: All partners.

Produced under Grant agreement No INEA/CEF/ICT/A2017/1564684 Europeana Media for the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency

Department C - Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) - TELECOMMUNICATIONS SECTOR

Europeana Media is a European Union co-funded project led by Istituto Luce Cinecittà srl (LUCE) - Italy. Partners are Netherlands Institute for Sounds and Vision (NISV) – Netherlands; Europeana Foundation (EF) – Netherlands; Noterik B.V. (NOTERIK) – Netherlands; Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB) – Germany, and Audiovisual Technologies, Informatics and Telecommunications (ATiT) – Belgium.

This publication reflects only the authors' view and that the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency of the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

**This project is co-funded by
the European Union**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- EXECUTIVE SUMMARY..... 4
 - Evaluation Goal, Questions, and Objectives..... 4
 - Methods 4
 - Findings..... 5
- METHODOLOGY..... 6
 - Participants..... 7
 - Presentation of Tasks and Analysis 7
 - Online Questionnaire Analysis 8
- FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS 12
 - Findings..... 12
 - Exploratory Tasks..... 12
 - Actual Scenario Tasks 14
 - Usability Metrics..... 19
 - Recommendations..... 30
- SUMMATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE FIRST AND SECOND EVALUATIONS RESULTS 31
- CONCLUSION 32
- APPENDICES..... 33
 - Appendix 1: Form_WP_3_3.2_01_1_3 (Sample) 33
 - Appendix 2: Form_WP_3_3.2_02_1..... 34
 - Appendix 3: Form_WP_3_3.2_02_2..... 35
 - Appendix 4: Confidence Level Questionnaire 36
 - Appendix 5: Likely Questions 37
 - Appendix 6: Usability Room Setup 38
 - Appendix 7: Usability Tasks 39
 - Appendix 8: Data Logging Sheet..... 44
 - Appendix 9: Problem Severity Descriptions 45
 - Bibliography..... 46

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Evaluation Goal, Questions, and Objectives

This document describes the usability evaluation of the second iteration of Europeana unified media player and video editor prototypes. The evaluation explored the features/functionality of the media player and video editor prototypes by 12 users drawn from three user groups defined in Activity 1¹.

The goal of the usability evaluation was to evaluate the changes made to the unified media player and video editor prototypes resulting from the first iteration² and to enrich them with objectively measured data.

The questions addressed were:

1. To what extent is the interaction architecture and design of the unified media player and video editor comprehensible to users?
2. Can the different user groups solve typical usage tasks satisfactorily?
3. Is the use of the unified media player and video editor comprehensible for the users even without a long acclimatization phase? (intuitiveness)
4. Are all controls recognized and understood?
5. Can users find all the information they need in the unified player and video editor?

The usability evaluation objectives were:

1. Determine design inconsistencies and usability problem areas within the user interface and content areas of the unified player and item page and the video editor. Potential sources of error may include:
 - i. Navigation errors – failure to locate functions, excessive keystrokes to complete a function, failure to follow recommended screen flow.
 - ii. Presentation errors – failure to locate and properly act upon desired information in screens, selection errors due to labeling ambiguities.
 - iii. Control usage problems – improper toolbar or entry field usage.
2. Exercise the web application under controlled test conditions with representative users. The data collected will be used to assess whether the usability goals regarding effective, efficient, and satisfactory media player and video editor interfaces have been achieved.
3. Establish baseline user performance and user-satisfaction levels of the player and video editor interfaces for future usability evaluations.

Methods

There were four users each from the research, education, and the general public user groups. There was a pilot test before the actual tests, and the usability test took place face-to-face in a lab setting.

The second iteration usability test of the Europeana Enhanced Unified Player prototype took place from 2-4 December 2019 on the 2nd-floor Grunwaldhaus, German National Library for Science and Technology Hannover. The second version of the video editor prototype has four basic functionalities, namely embed, annotation, subtitle, and playlist creation. All twelve participants tested the stated functionalities. The test files

¹ Please refer to Europeana Media proposal.

² The report of the first iteration usability evaluation is accessible at <https://zenodo.org/record/3478118#.XfzXbBtCdaR>

were accessed online as HTML files. The evaluation of the enhanced unified media player and video editor followed the guidelines specified in the usability evaluation plan document.

Findings

The outcomes of the usability evaluation present some interesting findings. First, there is 100% completion rates for four out of the five tasks, namely search, embed, annotate, and subtitle a video. Only the playlist task has a completion rate of 83%. Two of the participants received some assistance to complete the playlist task in one way or another. Secondly, the confidence rate is very high for all the tasks except for the video playlist creation task. The implication is that the participants felt highly confident to accomplish their assigned tasks. Thirdly, none of the tasks took longer than 230 seconds to complete. Participants feel impressed with the visual layout of the media player and the video editor. Participants are also satisfied with the ease of use and simplicity of the media player and the video editor. Participants felt more satisfied with the time for completing their tasks and with the ease of completion of tasks. Participants were, nevertheless, least satisfied with the lack of support information such as hints and tutorials. The average user satisfaction score for the media player is 90, and the average score for the video editor is 79. Overall, the average satisfaction score of both the media player and video editor is 85. This score is an excellent score based on the System Usability Scale scores' interpretations.

There are a total of 15 usability issues. They are mostly minor issues or some suggestions thought to be useful to improve the usability of the media player and video editor. There is a section describing the findings in detail and the recommendations in this report. The major usability issue is to fix the automatic playing of the video player in the media player when switching to the video editor. Furthermore, participants would like the media player to work with keyboard shortcuts, and tutorial and relevant help support integrated with the video editor to benefit first-time users. It is necessary to add a feature to remove a video from a video playlist and make the plus button more intuitive for users. The media player frame's size should be consistent and made to fit a portion of the page. Users do not have to scroll up or down and/or left or right of the page.

A summative analysis of the results of the first and second usability evaluations shows very promising insights. Firstly, the average task completion rate increased from 78% to 92%. Secondly, the average task completion time improved from 178.22 seconds to 159.80 seconds. Finally, the overall system usability satisfaction improved tremendously from 57 (OK) to 85 (excellent).

METHODOLOGY

Twelve participants comprising four researchers, four educators, and four people from the general public took part as evaluators in the second iteration of the usability evaluation of the Europeana unified media player and video editor. All the participants were selected using the purposive sampling technique and found through snowball sampling. They had worked with videos for one purpose or another. The equipment/materials used for the tests were:

- Hardware: Notebook with the prototype, mouse, webcam, power cord.
- Software: OBS Studio picture in picture screen recording open source software.
- Europeana unified media player and video editor prototypes (html files).
- Infrastructure: High Speed Internet.
- Browser application such as Firefox, and Chrome.
- Interview Guide.
- Consent form for audio and video recording.
- Writing materials.
- Video and photographic cameras for test documentation.

Before each test, there were pre-session interviews in which participants filled a short online questionnaire (via Google Form). The bases for the questions were:

- Participant's background.
- Experience with media player and video editor
- Rationale for using media player and video editor.
- Current online platforms used.

Similarly, participants were asked a few subjective questions in post-session interviews, and the bases of the questions were:

- Ease of completing each task
- Satisfaction about the tasks
- Overall ease of use
- Overall satisfaction
- Likes and dislikes about the unified media player and video editor (prototypes)
- Users' recommendations or suggestions for improving the unified media player and video editor.

The participants filled four questionnaires each during/at the end of their tests. The first two questionnaires were for assessing task-level satisfaction, and the adapted After-Scenario Questionnaire (ASQ)³ (Appendix 1) was presented after participants performed a task. The Confidence Level Questionnaire (Appendix 4) was also presented immediately after completing a task to indicate to what extent the task participant felt confident with completing the task. The second set of questionnaires was for determining the test level satisfaction and was adapted from the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire⁴ (Appendices 2 and 3). The test level satisfaction questionnaires were presented at the end of the test session. One (Appendix 2) was to evaluate participants' satisfaction with the media player, and the other (Appendix 3) was to evaluate satisfaction with the video editor.

The specific questions for pre-session and post-session interviews can be seen in Appendix 5.

³ <https://garyperlman.com/quest/quest.cgi?form=ASQ>

⁴ <https://www.usability.gov/how-to-and-tools/methods/system-usability-scale.html>

Participants

Twelve test participants were drawn and comprised of four researchers, four educators, and four users from the general public. As the sampling is purposive, all the participants should have used audiovisual media for varying needs or at least are familiar with Europeana. The basis for the selection of participants was their availability, willingness to participate, and professional use of, and experience with videos.

The participants' responsibilities were to attempt to perform a set of representative task scenarios presented to them in as efficient and timely a manner as possible and to provide feedback concerning the usability and acceptability of the unified media player and video editor. The participants had to provide honest opinions regarding the usability of the media player and video editor and to participate in pre and post sessions interviews, post-session subjective questionnaires, and debriefing.

Very few bugs were initially experienced but were promptly fixed and did not affect the results of the tests negatively. The bugs were:

1. The video embed slider and video size options did not appear, and the web page had to be refreshed.
2. Media player frame sizes initially appeared larger and then tiny but were fixed.
3. A lengthy text appeared below a video and hid the plus button on the playlist tab. A participant had to scroll down the page to see the plus button.

The Tables below summarize the participants' breakdown of groups and gender. All the educators are from higher education institutions.

Table 1: User groups

User group	#
Educator	4
Researcher	4
General Public	4
Total	12

Table 2: Gender

Gender	#
Male	6
Female	6
Total	12

Presentation of Tasks and Analysis

Using a typical lab set up, a laptop computer with the media player and video editor prototypes, and supporting the Europeana item page, were used. The facilitator sitting in the same room monitored participants' interactions with the prototypes. A note-taker/data logger observed the test sessions in the same room. All the test sessions were video-recorded. The facilitator briefed the participants on the unified media player and video editor prototypes and instructed them that they are evaluating the application, rather than the facilitator evaluating them. Participants signed an informed consent that acknowledged their participation was voluntary, participation can cease at any time, the session will be videotaped, and privacy and identification will be safeguarded. The facilitator asked if the participants had any questions. The facilitator explained that the amount of time taken to complete the test task will be measured and that there should be no exploratory behavior outside the task flow until after task completion. At the start of each task, the

participant read aloud the task description from the printed copy and began the task. Time-on-task measurement began when the participant started the task. The test was in two parts: first, participants explored both the media player and video editor. Secondly, participants performed a set of scenarios tasks. The entire test session took approximately 60 minutes. Participants completed a pretest demographic and background information questionnaire via a Google form link.

The facilitator instructed the participant to ‘think aloud’ so that a verbal record exists of their interaction with the unified media player and video editor prototypes. The facilitator and observer both observed and entered user behavior, user comments, and system actions in the data logging application (usability datalogger 5.1.1 – a free open source excel application developed by Todd Zazelenchuk, Ph.D.).

After each task, each participant completed the post-task questionnaire (ASQ and Confidence Level Questionnaire) and elaborated on the task session with the facilitator. After all task scenarios were attempted, the participant completed the post-test satisfaction questionnaires (SUS) and answered the post-session short interview.

Online Questionnaire Analysis

Participants completed a pretest demographic and background information questionnaire via a Google form. The following figures explain their experiences and expectations regarding the use of videos and media players.

Figure 1: Platforms used by the 12 participants (**Please note these are responses to a multiple and free choice question)

Table 3: Participants' background experience

User group	Participants	Age	Video use purposes	Video editor used	Editorial tasks	Experience with video editors
Educator (All from Higher Education)	P1	27	Entertainment, Classroom teaching aid	iMovie	Annotation, Subtitle, Chapterise, Summarise, Tagging, Segmentation	Less than one year
	P5	42	Entertainment	Windows media player	None	First time
	P10	40	Learning new things	Premiere pro CC, Viva video app, H5P	Tagging, Clipping	More than 10 years
	P12	32	Entertainment, Classroom teaching aid	Video ant, Camtasia, Windows media player	Annotation, Segmentation	More than one year but less than 5 years
General Public	P2	29	Entertainment, Research analysis	Adobe after effects, Adobe premiere, cinema4d	Creating animations	First time
	P4	25	Entertainment, Research analysis, understanding study topics	None	Playlist	First time
	P7	24	Entertainment, research analysis, supplementary material for publication	Windows movie maker, smartphone apps	Subtitle, Playlist, Tagging	More than one year but less than 5 years
	P8	50	MOOCs, Presentation	YouTube, Vimeo	Embed	First time
Researcher	P3	50	Entertainment, Classroom teaching aid, research analysis, supplementary material for publication, Sharing	Test version of Europeana playout service, (usually does not use video editors)	Embed, Subtitle, Playlist, Tagging, Segmentation, Export descriptive metadata	Less than one year
	P6	53	Entertainment, research analysis, supplementary material for publication	Adobe premiere	Annotation, Embed, Subtitle, Playlist, Tagging	First time
	P9	37	Entertainment, Classroom teaching aid, supplementary material for publication, fundamental research material	iMovie	Annotation, Embed, Segmentation	More than one year but less than 5 years
	P11	47	Research analysis	None	Chapterise, Summarise, Tagging, Segmentation	First time

Table 3 shows that the majority of the participants use video for entertainment and profession, for example, research or education. Both educators and researchers use videos as a visual aid to support classroom teaching. It is a known fact that researchers and educators in universities and research institutions engage in research and teaching. Similarly, three of the participants from the general public use videos for research analysis. Two participants, P4 and P7, are postgraduate students from higher institutions, and they use videos for class presentations. Furthermore, the two participants indicate that sometimes, they use videos in some of their courses, such as media learning in the post-test interview.

The participants responded with a wide variety of applications and services to question 4, asking them to list video editors they have used or indicate none. A number of the names are real video editors such as iMovie

(named by 2 participants), Premiere (named by 3 participants), Viva video, and Windows movie maker. Some participants mentioned the use of services that are not native video editing tools but allow editing: services such as Camtasia (a screencast recorder/editor) or YouTube with its auxiliary online editor. Other participants referred to tools that allow one or the other enhanced function with video, but generally speaking, are not editors as such. These tools are h5p (a tool to make interactive HTML5 content), Video Ant (a web-based video annotation tool), After Effects (a digital effects software), cinema4d (3D software). The rest of the tools and services used are players (Windows Media Player), a test version of Europeana playout service, the video portal Vimeo and apps in general. Two participants explicitly state that here they have not used any video editor at all before.

With regards to question 5: “How long have you been using video editors on online platforms or repositories?” 6 out of the 12 participants indicate that they are first time users. Question 6, “What editorial tasks the participants do with videos?”, gives an idea of what tasks participants were more or less familiar with, and explains at the same time the selection of tools and services mentioned under question 4. In Figure 2, we can see the frequency of the tasks participants refer to in their answers to the tasks offered as a multiple-choice question:

Figure 2: Video editing tasks by the 12 participants (Please note these are responses to a multiple and free choice question)**

Besides choosing among tasks, participants also could add free-text answers. The tasks mentioned once are Clipping, Creating animations, and Export descriptive metadata. Only one participant explicitly responded, ‘None’.

Figure 3: Features support the 12 participants look for in a media player (Please note these are responses to a multiple and free choice question)**

Figure 4: Features that give 9 of the participants, positive experience (Please note these are responses to an open ended question. ***One participant has a negative experience, two participants have neutral experience.)**

Overall, it seems that the experiences of the participants are very mixed. First, their experience ranged from none at all to quite extensive professional experience. Furthermore, their experiences vary with degrees of specific scenarios of use of the Europeana Media player/editor.

FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Findings

Table 4 is the description of participants and their corresponding user groups.

Table 4: Participants' codes

Participants' code	Age	User groups' code	User group
P1	27	Edu_1	Educator
P2	29	Gen_1	General Public
P3	50	Res_1	Researcher
P4	25	Gen_2	General Public
P5	42	Edu_2	Educator
P6	53	Res_2	Researcher
P7	24	Gen_3	General Public
P8	50	Gen_4	General Public
P9	37	Res_3	Researcher
P10	40	Edu_3	Educator
P11	47	Res_4	Researcher
P12	32	Edu_4	Educator

Exploratory Tasks

Exploration of the Unified Media Player

Participants had a link (<https://europeana.video-editor.eu/en>), where they accessed the media player online. Participants expressed their initial reactions to the media player. They interacted with the player controls, play/pause, volume, full-screen view, and other buttons with their mouse and watched sample videos briefly. Some of the initial comments are presented as follows:

Figure 5: Two of the participants exploring the media player

P1 - "looks very simple and nothing is really difficult for me"

P2 - "Nothing to make me struggle, it is clear to use"

P3 - "It is clear and nice to use. One thing I like with the YouTube when you look for certain content in the video and then it shows you this small visuals with the frame, so that you can quickly find what you are looking for within the video."

P1 - "What I don't like is that it is bigger than the actual page, I have to scroll down to see the button. Would be nice if it is a little bit smaller (player frame)"

P1 - "I really like that the more options pop up in the media player, because sometimes it is on the other sides, left or right. I think the options are really good, I would be intrigued to see what I can do with it"

P4 - "I think it is very intuitive. It is similar to the YouTube". I was just curious about what the three dots are but I can see I can create something with the functions"

P6 - "It is good, simple, (but) I missed the share button"

P11 - "I think the usability is for me what it should be about."

Overall all the participants had initial good impressions about the layout of the media player and the interface, control buttons, etc.

Exploration of the Video Editor

Participants also freely explored the video editor and saw what it offers. Participants had initial good impressions of the layout of the video editor. They thought the GUI has a good visual design, and control buttons, task tabs, can be easily recognized and understood. Nevertheless, some of them had some initial struggles.

P4 - "It is easy to understand how to create a playlist"

P5 - "I would think the enter button (from the keyboard) is for entering the subtitle but you go to the next line (instead)"

Figure 6: Another two of the participants performing some exploratory tasks.

P1 - "Would be nice to have all these subtitles and see them in there as well"

Note:

P1 wanted to create subtitles in more than one language for the current video and display them simultaneously.

P1 - "I would like to have a speech bubble"

(P1 Wanted to create "speech bubble" annotation but only note annotation was supported.)

P1 - "I can edit the name but can't add another playlist, so it is just one playlist at a time"

(P1 wanted to create a new playlist in the same session.)

P2 - "I can create subtitles but it is not giving me subtitles" This is the way I understand it now, I can use this button to create subtitles for the video, is this right?"

P2 was confused with the button “create subtitle”, he thought he could generate the subtitles automatically by clicking this button.

P3 - “It is a clear and nice design I would say. I like the typography.”

P3 would like to see the transcript of the default language to create subtitles in another language. She feels it is easier to create subtitles in this way.

P3 feels not only scientists would benefit from the editor’s use but the broader public because they can at least share videos.

P5 - “I think it is simple to use (but) sometimes it would be good to have a little explanations (about the functionalities)” “I think you will find it if you look around but it would be faster if you add a little bit of explanations.”

P7 – “It is pretty structured. It is not too much, just the information (features) you need.” “I can move it to the position you want (subtitles)”

P11 - “May be I will use this video editor in future but for me it is not that usable as I wish it to be.”

P12 – “It could be really helpful for analyzing a video.”

P9 – “The layout is very good. There is no visual overload.”

Overall, the exploratory tasks gave the participants opportunities to interact with the media player and the video editor. The insights gained are that most of the participants understood how the player and editor work, and this gives the impression that the learning of the player and editor can be quick.

Actual Scenario Tasks

Table 5 is the list of tasks for the 12 participants.

Table 5: Tasks list

#	Task	User group
1	Search for a video	All
2	Create a video clip and embed	All
3	Annotate a video with notes	All
4	Create subtitles for a video	All
5	Create a playlist of a video and three bookmarked videos	All

Task: Search for a video

All the participants searched for the prescribed video successfully.

Figure 7: Participants searched for required videos successfully.

The search functionality worked very well for all the participants.

Task: Create a video embed

Figure 8: Video clipping and embedding

A participant struggled as a first time user but managed to complete the task successfully. Another participant desires the option to type in the start time and end time manually.

Task: Annotate a video with notes

Some participants were editing the timer instead of using the timing up and down controls. Annotation types were also not understood.

Figure 9: Video annotation issues.

Task: Create subtitles for a video

Some participants wrongly pressed the enter key from the keyboard and thought their texts were saved.

Figure 10A: Video subtitle text box issues.

Figure 10B: Video subtitle text box and plus button issues.

A participant entered multiple lines of texts.

The plus button was not so intuitive for many of the participants. Some of them suggest a label or descriptive button.

Figure 10C: Video subtitle pause video while typing feature issue.

Some participants struggled with this feature.

Figure 10D: Video subtitle text box closes abruptly.

Subtitle text box closes too abruptly when the video is paused and annoying for some participants.

Figure 10E: Video subtitle display issue.

Subtitle in preview: a participant was confused about how the subtitle would display.

Task: Create a playlist of a video and three bookmarked videos

Figure 11: A video playlist issue.

Usability Metrics

Usability metrics refer to user performance measured against specific performance goals necessary to satisfy usability requirements. Scenario completion success rates, error rates, and subjective evaluations, and Time-to-completion of scenarios were analysed.

Task Completion Rate

The completion rate is the percentage of test participants who complete the task without critical errors. A critical error ends in an incorrect or incomplete outcome. In other words, the completion rate represents the percentage of participants who, upon finishing with the specified task, have an "output" that is correct. A failed task is such that a participant asks for assistance to produce the correct output. A task is easy if the participant did not make more than one attempt to complete it. A medium performance is such when the user makes two attempts to get the task done. A task is hard if the participant makes three attempts or more to get it done.

A completion rate of 100% was the goal for each task. Similarly, an error-free rate of 80% was the goal of each task.

Figure 12: Task performance by the 12 participants.

As can be seen in Figure 12, all the participants completed the search task for a video with ease. Only the playlist task had to be completed with some assistance by 2 participants. Overall, the task completion rate for all tasks was 100% except for the playlist task, which was 83%. There were no critical errors except a few bugs initially experienced. Some participants only had to make more than one attempt to complete embed, annotation, subtitling, and playlist tasks.

Task Completion and Confidence Levels

Confidence levels are based on a 7-scale rating of how confident a participant feels with completing a task. Figure 13 indicates all the participants have high confidence above 70% with all the tasks, except for the playlist task, which is on an average of 67%. Two participants completed the playlist task with some assistance. Furthermore, some of the participants feel they could have completed the aspect of video bookmarking by themselves instead of being done for them before the task.

Figure 13: Task completion and confidence ratings of the 12 participants.

Time on Task (TOT)

The time to complete a scenario is referred to as time on task. It is measured from when the person begins the scenario to the time he/she indicates completion. Figure 14 is the results obtained regarding task completion time by the 12 participants.

Figure 14: Task completion time by the 12 participants.

The results show participants spent the most time to complete the annotation task. This is so because the annotation and subtitle tasks required more steps to complete compared to the rest tasks. The major challenge with the playlist is the plus button, which some of the participants could not quickly understand as the button is required to add the bookmarked videos. Furthermore, there was a video with a lengthy text description below and hides the plus button from the participant. Finally, some of the participants were first time users of a web-based video editor and performing some of the tasks for the first time. The tasks mostly well-known to the participants appear to be the annotation and video subtitling tasks.

Problem Severity

Table 6 is an overview of the severity assessment of usability problems identified. The results indicate there are no critical usability problems with the media player and the video editor.

Table 6: Problem severity assessments

Task	Severity	Issues
Search	None	None
Embed a video	3	Initial bugs with the timing slider and video size selection were promptly corrected.
Annotate a video	3	Lack of distinction of annotation types annoyed some participants. Few participants edited the timer instead of using the time up/down buttons.
Subtitle a video	3	Text box closed abruptly when participants wanted to pause a video.
Create a video playlist	4	A video with lengthy texts below it hide the plus button.

Impact

The impact is the ranking of the consequences of the problem by defining the level of impact that the problem has on successful task completion. There are three levels of impact:

- High - prevents the user from completing the task (critical error)
- Moderate - causes user difficulty but the task can be completed (non-critical error)
- Low - minor problems that do not significantly affect task completion (non-critical error)

Frequency

Frequency is the percentage of participants who experience the problem when working on a task.

- High: 60% or more of the participants experience the problem
- Moderate: 21% - 59% of participants experience the problem
- Low: 20% or fewer of the participants experience the problem

Problem Severity Classification

The identified severity for each problem implies a general reward for resolving it, and a general risk for not addressing it, in the current release.

Severity 1

These are high impact problems that often prevent a user from correctly completing a task. They occur in varying frequency and are characteristic of calls to the Help Desk. The reward for resolution is typically exhibited in fewer Help Desk calls and reduced redevelopment costs.

Severity 2

Moderate to high-frequency problems with moderate to low impact are typical of erroneous actions that the participant recognizes needs to be undone. The reward for resolution is typically exhibited in reduced time on task and decreased training costs.

Severity 3

Either moderate problems with low frequency or low problems with moderate frequency; these are minor annoyance problems, faced by some participants. The reward for resolution is typically exhibited in reduced time on task and increased data integrity.

Severity 4

Low impact problems are faced by a few participants, and there is a low risk of not resolving these problems. The reward for resolution is typically exhibited in increased user satisfaction.

Subjective Measures

We surveyed subjective opinions about specific tasks, time to perform each task, features, and functionality. At the end of the test, participants rated their satisfaction with the overall system (the unified media player prototype). The attitudes of the participants were assessed using the data from the subjective evaluation and the interview/debriefing session.

Task Level Satisfaction

Figure 15 is the overall assessment of the result of task-level satisfaction by the 12 participants. The results indicate that the participants were least satisfied with the lack of support information such as help, tutorials, and hints to complete most of their tasks.

Figure 15: Task level satisfaction assessments of the 12 participants.

Test Level Satisfaction

Figures 16, 17, and 18 are the results of satisfaction assessments of the 12 participants with the media player. The results show a high level of satisfaction by all the user groups with the media player. The average satisfaction score for the three groups for the media player is 90.

Figure 16: Test level satisfaction assessments of the educator user group.

Figure 17: Test level satisfaction assessments of the researcher user group.

Figure 18: Test level satisfaction assessments of the general public user group for the media player.

Similarly, Figures 19, 20, and 21 are the results of satisfaction assessments of the 12 participants with the video editor. The results also show a high level of satisfaction by all the user groups with the video editor. The average satisfaction score for the three groups with the video editor is 79. Overall, the average satisfaction score for both the media player and video editor is 85, which is excellent according to the system usability scale interpretations⁵. It should be noted that the video editor is integrated with the media player and opens in a new window on a web page.

Figure 19: Test level satisfaction assessments of the educator user group for the video editor.

⁵ Please see <https://measuringu.com/interpret-sus-score/>

Figure 20: Test level satisfaction assessments of the researcher user group for the video editor.

Figure 21: Test level satisfaction assessments of the general public user group for the video editor.

Post Test Interviews

Figures 22 to 28 are an overview of the post-interview results.

Figure 22: Participants' visit to Europeana.eu.

As can be seen in Figure 22, eight of the participants had visited the Europeana platform, and four of them have not. Figure 23 is a description of their visiting purposes.

Figure 23: Types of content found by 8 participants who had visited Europeana.eu.

The 12 participants were verbally asked about their overall impressions with the media player and the video editor also during the post-test interview. Their responses were transcribed into texts and analysed thematically. Figures 24 and 25 are the themes, which emerged from the analysis of their verbal responses.

Figure 24: Overall impressions of the 12 with the media player. (Note that multiple impressions were made in some instances. *** impressions indicated in red colour are negative)**

Figure 25: Overall impressions of the 12 participants with the video editor. (**Note that multiple impressions were made in some instances. *** impressions indicated in red colour are negative)

Figure 26: Usage scenarios envisioned for a video editor. (**Note that multiple scenarios were indicated in some instances)

Figure 27: Significant changes suggested for the media player.

Figure 28: Significant changes suggested for the video editor.

Overall, eight participants said yes, they would recommend the player and its editor, and three participants would recommend if everything works fine and relevant to the need of their colleagues. One is not so sure.

Recommendations

Key Observation:

Video always plays automatically in the media player when a user switches to the editor. This should be corrected because all the participants found it very annoying.

Table 7: Recommendation lists

Issues	Recommendations	What is affected?
No forward/backward buttons	Include forward and backward buttons to the player if need be. However, the media player has a scrub function to move the video forward and backward, and this suggestion is a very minor recommendation.	Media Player
No keyboard shortcuts	Synchronize essential buttons in the media player such as play/pause, volume up/down, and mute with appropriate keyboard buttons.	
Video play automatically when switching to the editor	Fix this bug. It distracted and annoyed all the participants.	
Media player inconsistent frame size	Keep a unique and consistent player frame size that does not require the user to scroll up/down and/or left/right the page.	
No tutorial support	Include tutorials to explain how the video editor works and the key features. "I am not always sure what these things (annotation types) are" – P6	Video editor
Plus button not intuitive enough	Change the plus button to a label if need be, but the user could master its use with two or three trials (the mouse over message is helpful all the same). "I didn't see this plus button at first." – P12 "Where do I type?" – P9	
No feature option to remove a video from playlist	Include a feature option to remove a video from the playlist.	
Annotation types not distinct when displayed	Make annotation types to appear distinctly. For example, the speech bubble and spotlight icons could contain the texts and appear directly on the video. "I have chosen spotlight annotation, it appears the same way as my speech bubble annotation" – P11 "I am just wondering, what is the difference between the speech bubble and the notes." - P12 "What is the difference between speech bubble and spotlight?" – P9	
Long playlist	Position the list to the right. "Maybe if you have (about) 50 videos and you are making a playlist, the side becomes very long. Maybe a list on the right side would be very helpful." – P7	
Time framing (annotation)	"Referring to the time code, it is 47.68. It would be brilliant to have not only the seconds but the frames per second. Maybe 1min, 47 frame 16. Very often films are made with 18 frames per second, 24 frames per second." – P11. This is a very minor recommendation.	
Auto generated subtitles	Include the option to see the original transcript and generate new transcripts using automatic speech recognition.	
Multiple language subtitles	If possible include functionality to add subtitles to a video in multiple languages.	
Slow motion option for subtitling	Include slow-motion functionality to make adding subtitles easier. The video editor has built-in functionalities to allow users to pause the video while typing and scrub functionality to move the video forward and backward. This suggestion is also a minor recommendation.	
Subtitle display in preview	Show the subtitles on the video once the user clicks the subtitle button to reduce the complexity of displaying subtitles. "...I didn't realise I have to click on it (the language displayed). Maybe in the default setting the subtitles should start" – P12	
Text box closes too abruptly	Perhaps leave the text box open until the user presses the plus or save buttons. "This thing (text box) always closes when you press the film (click the play button)" "Anytime I clicked (the closed text box), I am 5 secs behind" – p9	

SUMMATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE FIRST AND SECOND EVALUATIONS RESULTS

The results of the second usability evaluation suggest there have been lots of improvements regarding the usability of the media player and the video editor. The implication of the results of the first usability evaluation is the need to carry out a major redesign of the video player and editor. Some buttons had to be removed to eliminate the system’s redundancy, and some buttons had to be repositioned to be consistent with standard designs of similar systems. It can be seen currently from the initial impressions, actual tasks, and overall assessments that participants feel more satisfied with both the media player and the video editor. The table below is the comparison between the first and second usability evaluations.

Table 8: Summative Evaluation

Key Metrics	First Evaluation	Second Evaluation
Average Task Completion Rate	78%	92%
Average Task Completion Time	178.22 secs	159.80 secs
Overall System Usability Satisfaction	57 (OK)	85 (Excellent)

The results, overall, suggest that the current usability satisfaction for both the media player and video editor is excellent but can and should be improved. A satisfaction score of 100 is the best imaginable.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the usability of the media player and video editor has improved when compared with the outcomes of the first usability evaluation with the current report. Participants feel impressed with the media player, and video editor and first-time users can learn to use the system quickly in an efficient, effective, and satisfactory manner, notably if they are equipped with some help options such as hints and tutorials. A short text/graphic tutorial that describes how the editor works would be beneficial for first-time users who lacked prior scientific video editing experience. The design layouts were perceived to be simple, have good visuals, and easy to use. The buttons and controls were understood by most of the participants, and first-time video editor users performed assigned tasks successfully. The usability of the media player and video should improve with the implementation of key recommendations made.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Form_WP_3_3.2_01_1_3 (Sample)

Task-Level Satisfaction Questionnaire

Please rate to what extent you perceived the task you have just completed. Please indicate by ticking the appropriate box with an (X).

Name	User group: General Public	Date
------	----------------------------	------

Task:

S/N	ITEM		1	2	3	4	5	6	7		n/a	
1.	Overall, I am satisfied with the ease of completing the tasks in this scenario.	Strongly disagree									Strongly agree	
2.	Overall, I am satisfied with the amount of time it took to complete the tasks in this scenario.	Strongly disagree									Strongly agree	
3.	Overall, I am satisfied with the support information (hints, prompts, messages) when completing the tasks.	Strongly disagree									Strongly agree	

Appendix 2: Form_WP_3_3.2_02_1

Test-Level Satisfaction Questionnaire

Please rate to what extent you agree or otherwise with the following statements based on the system you just tested. Please indicate by ticking the appropriate box with an (X).

Name	Date
------	------

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree
	1	2	3	4	5
I think that I would like to use this media player frequently.					
I found the media player unnecessarily complex.					
I thought the media player was easy to use.					
I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this media player.					
I found the various functions in this media player were well integrated.					
I thought there was too much inconsistency in this media player.					
I would imagine that most people would learn to use this media player very quickly.					
I found the media player very difficult to use.					
I felt very confident using the media player.					
I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this media player.					

Appendix 3: Form_WP_3_3.2_02_2

Test-Level Satisfaction Questionnaire

Please rate to what extent you agree or otherwise with the following statements based on the system you just tested. Please indicate by ticking the appropriate box with an (X).

Name	Date
------	------

	Strongly disagree	2	3	4	Strongly agree
	1	2	3	4	5
I think that I would like to use this video editor frequently.					
I found the video editor unnecessarily complex.					
I thought the video editor was easy to use.					
I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this video editor.					
I found the various functions in this video editor were well integrated.					
I thought there was too much inconsistency in this video editor.					
I would imagine that most people would learn to use this video editor very quickly.					
I found the video editor very difficult to use.					
I felt very confident using the video editor.					
I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this video editor.					

Appendix 4: Confidence Level Questionnaire

Participant code:

Main task:

How confident were you with completing this task?

Please circle one option from 1 to 7.

Low	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	High
-----	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	------

Appendix 5: Likely Questions

Pre-Session Short Questionnaire

1. On which web platform(s) do you use access videos? List them.
2. What do you often do with videos?
3. What types of information or support do you look for in a media player?
4. Which video editor(s) have you used? Please list them or indicate none.
5. How long have you been using video editors on online platforms or repositories?
6. What editorial tasks do you do with videos?
7. Do any of the media players and or video editors you used have features to help make your experience positive? explain briefly why

Post-Session Interview

1. What are your overall impressions of the media player and the video editor?
2. What typical usage scenario do you anticipate for the media player and video editor? Would you use them?
3. What are the three things you like best about the unified media player?
4. If you could make one significant change to this unified media player and or the video editor, what change would you make?
5. Have you used contents in europeana.eu before? Which content was that?
6. What was the content used for?
7. Would you recommend the media player to a colleague and video editor to a friend or colleague?
8. Do you have any other questions or comments about the media player or your experiences with it?

Appendix 6: Usability Room Setup

Appendix 7: Usability Tasks

Exploratory Questions (all user groups)

Unified Media Player and Video Editor

Task 1

This is Europeana enhanced unified media player. Please give me your initial reactions to this media player. Feel free to explore this media player as you normally would. You can interact with the player controls; play/pause, volume, full screen view, and other buttons with your mouse, but please don't click on the 'more' button (the three dots) just yet.

Facilitator will ask:

- Have you ever seen this media player before?
- Please give me your initial impressions about the layout of this media player and what you think of the interface, control buttons, etc.
- Without clicking on anything from the 'more' button yet, please describe the options you see on the 'more' button and what you think they do. Feel free to move around the page, but again I'll ask you not to click on anything right now.
- Without clicking on anything yet, if you were exploring, what would you click on first?
- What do you think is the purpose of this media player?
- Who do you think this media player is intended for?

Task 2

You have five minutes to freely explore this media player. You may play the video, but please remember to speak aloud as you do so. You would also like to interact with the video editor and see what it offers. I will tell you when the five minutes are up.

Facilitator will ask:

- Have you ever seen this video editor before?
- Please give me your initial impressions about the layout of this video editor and what you think of the interface, control buttons, task tabs, etc.
- Without clicking on anything yet, if you were exploring, what would you click on first?
- What do you think is the purpose of this video editor?
- Who do you think this video editor is intended for?

Scenario Tasks

Research user group

Task 3 – Clipping and embed

You are a scientist and an editor of an online scientific magazine. You are preparing for an editorial article on Bat co-evolution with humans. You came to <https://europeana.video-editor.eu/>. Your colleague had informed you about an interesting video published by the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision on Europeana. The video is titled "Researching the bat migration". You would like to search for this video and embed a clip of the video from 00:00 to 01:25. You prefer your clip to be 960 x 720 and your online platform supports iframe embed. How would you do these?

When you feel you have completed this task, please say so.

Task 4 – Annotate and subtitle

You are a scientist studying animal behavior. You are preparing an article to describe how lions can get a medical treatment. You were searching and saw an interesting short video titled “Stado lwów w warszawskim” on Europeana. The publisher, Filmoteka Narodowa gives a free access to reuse the video for non-commercial purpose. You decide to use the video as a supplementary material for your article. The video is in polish but your readers are English-speaking.

First, you decide to annotate the video with note type annotations.

Second, you want to subtitle the video into English.

How would you do these?

When you feel you have completed this task, please say so.

Task 5 – Playlist

You wanted to create a new documentary video playlist on everyday life. You were searching and found an interesting video but not titled. You watched this video a bit (the link is opened for you). You decided to go to the playlist tab on the video editor. You also want to add three other videos you have earlier bookmarked on europeana to your playlist (the bookmarking has been done for you). You want to start creating your playlist. Your playlist would be copied to your blog platform. How would you do these?

Educator user group

Task 3 – Clipping and embed

You are an educator and an editor of an online educational magazine. You are preparing for an editorial article on Bat co-evolution with humans. You came to <https://europeana.video-editor.eu/>. Your colleague had informed you about an interesting video published by the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision on Europeana. The video is titled “Researching the bat migration”. You would like to search for this video and embed a clip of the video from 00:00 to 01:25. You prefer your clip to be 960 x 720 and your online platform supports iframe embed. How would you do these?

Task 4 – Annotate and subtitle

You are going to teach some lessons on animal behavior. You are preparing a lesson to describe how lions can get a medical treatment. You were searching and saw an interesting short video titled “Stado lwów w warszawskim” on Europeana. The publisher, Filmoteka Narodowa gives a free access to reuse the video for non-commercial purpose. You decide to use the video as a visual aid for your lesson. The video is in polish but your students are Deutsch-speaking.

First, you decide to annotate the video with note type annotations.

Second, you want to subtitle the video into Deutsch.

How would you do these?

Task 5 – Playlist

You wanted to create a new documentary video playlist on everyday life. You were searching and found an interesting video but not titled. You watched this video a bit (the link is opened for you). You decided to go to the playlist tab on the video editor. You also want to add three other videos you have earlier bookmarked on

Europeana to your playlist (the bookmarking has been done for you). You want to start creating your playlist. Your playlist would be copied to your blog platform. How would you do these?

General Public user group

Task 3 – Clipping and embed

You are an editor of an online news magazine. You are preparing for an editorial article on Bat co-evolution with humans. You came to <https://europeana.video-editor.eu/>. Your colleague had informed you about an interesting video published by the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision on Europeana. The video is titled “Researching the bat migration”. You would like to search for this video and embed a clip of the video from 00:00 to 01:25. You prefer your clip to be 960 x 720 and your online platform supports the Oembed format. How would you do these?

Task 4 – Annotate and subtitle

You are a social worker. You are preparing a presentation for a group of people on how to manage work abuse and unfair treatments. You were searching and saw an interesting short video titled “Dwie joasie” on Europeana. The publisher, Filmoteka Narodowa gives a free access to reuse the video for non-commercial purpose. You decide to use the video as a visual aid for your presentation. The video is in Polish but your audience is English-speaking.

First, you decide to annotate the video with note type annotations.

Second, you want to subtitle the video into English.

How would you do these?

Task 5 – Playlist

You wanted to create a new documentary video playlist on everyday life. You were searching and found an interesting video but not titled. You watched this video a bit (the link is opened for you). You decided to go to the playlist tab on the video editor. You also want to add three other videos you have earlier bookmarked on Europeana to your playlist (the bookmarking has been done for you). You want to start creating your playlist. Your playlist would be copied to your blog platform. How would you do these?

Expected steps to take:

Task 3 – Clipping and embed

Step 1: Go to <https://europeana.video-editor.eu/>.

Step 2: Type “Researching the bat migration” in the search box and press enter.

Step 3: Clicks the video from the result page.

Step 4: Click the play button first to watch the video.

Step 5: Click the “more” button to go to the editor.

Step 6: Click “create embed”. The embed tab on the video editor is opened.

Step 7: Drag the slider from the “end at” section to 01:25.

Step 8: Select 960 x 720 from the video size options.

Step 9: Select the required embed format.

Step 10: Click copy.

Step 11: Finalise the task in the third party environment using the copied embed code.

Task 4 – Annotate and subtitle

Step 1: Go to <https://europeana.video-editor.eu/>.

Step 2: Type “Stado lwów w warszawskim” or “Dwie joasie” (depending on the user group task scenario) in the search box and press enter.

Step 3: Clicks the video from the result page.

Step 4: Click the play button first to watch the video.

Step 5: Click the “more” button to go to the editor.

Step 6: Click “create annotations”. The annotation tab on the video editor is opened.

Step 7: Select “Note” from annotation type options.

Step 8: Move the video with the timer to desire points or drag with the slider.

Step 9: Type necessary texts to annotate the video as desired and click the save button. Repeat steps 8 and 9 as desired.

Step 10: Preview the annotated video.

Step 11: Copy the video as desired to your third party environment.

Step 12: Click “Subtitles” tab.

Step 13: Select the desired language to translate into.

Step 14: Check the “pause video while typing” box.

Step 15: Add subtitle texts as desired to the video.

Step 16: Preview the video

Step 17: Click “download” to download the subtitle script.

Task 5 – Playlist

Step 1: Go to <https://europeana.video-editor.eu/record/08637/1037479000000386003>.

Step 2: Click the play button first to watch the video.

Step 3: Click the “more” button to go to the editor.

Step 4: Click “create playlist”. The playlist tab on the video editor is opened in a new window.

Step 5: Type “Everyday life” in the playlist name text box or as desired.

Step 6: Click save.

Step 7: Click the “plus” “(+)” button to add the bookmarked videos.

Step 8: Add the three bookmarked videos in turn.

Step 9: Preview the annotated video if desired.

Step 10: Copy the video as desired to your third party environment.

Appendix 8: Data Logging Sheet

EUPS Usability Datalogger

Tasks
 Step 1: Enter tasks and indicate settings for each item.
 Step 2: Click **SAVE CHANGES** to see effect on P worksheets.

#	Task (aka Scenario/Question)	Chart Label	Scored	TaskCards	Random
1	You have heard about the unified media player on Europeana and would like to interact with it.	Explore EUPM	No	No	
2	You would also like to interact with the video editor and see what it offers.	Video editor	No	No	
3	Search a video on Europeana	Search	Yes	Yes	
4	Embed a video	Embed	Yes	Yes	
5	Annotate video using notes at interval of choice	Annotate	Yes	Yes	
6	Subtitle a video	Subtitle	Yes	Yes	
7	Create a video playlist	Playlist	Yes	Yes	
8		No	No		
9		No	No		
10		No	No		
11		No	No		
12		No	No		
13		No	No		
14		No	No		
15		No	No		
16		No	No		
17		No	No		
18		No	No		
19		No	No		
20		No	No		
21		No	No		
22		No	No		
23		No	No		
24		No	No		
25		No	No		
26		No	No		
27		No	No		
28		No	No		
29		No	No		
30		No	No		

Admin | Tasks | P1 | P2 | P3 | P4 | P5 | P6 | P7 | P8 | P9 | P10 | P11 | P12 | DataSum | DataCharts | Charts | Observations | PrintForms

Appendix 9: Problem Severity Descriptions

Problem severity arises from a combination of two factors –

1. The impact of the problem and;
2. The frequency of users experiencing the problem during the evaluation.

Scenario Completion

Each scenario requires, or requests, that the participant obtains or inputs specific data that would be used in the course of a typical task. The scenario is completed when the participant indicates the scenario's goal has been obtained (whether successfully or unsuccessfully) or the participant requests and receives sufficient guidance as to warrant scoring the scenario as a critical error.

Critical Errors

Critical errors are deviations at completion from the targets of the scenario. Obtaining or otherwise reporting of the wrong data value due to participant workflow is a critical error. Participants may or may not be aware that the task goal is incorrect or incomplete.

Independent completion of the scenario is a universal goal; help obtained from the other usability test roles is cause to score the scenario a critical error. Critical errors can also be assigned when the participant initiates (or attempts to initiate) an action that will result in the goal state becoming unobtainable. In general, critical errors are unresolved errors during the process of completing the task or errors that produce an incorrect outcome.

Non-critical Errors

Non-critical errors are errors that are recovered from by the participant or, if not detected, do not result in processing problems or unexpected results. Although non-critical errors can be undetected by the participant, when they are detected they are generally frustrating to the participant.

These errors may be procedural, in which the participant does not complete a scenario in the most optimal means (e.g., excessive steps and keystrokes). These errors may also be errors of confusion (for example, initially selecting the wrong function, using a user-interface control incorrectly such as attempting to edit an un-editable field).

Noncritical errors can always be recovered from during the process of completing the scenario. Exploratory behavior, such as opening the wrong menu while searching for a function, will be coded as a non-critical error.

Subjective Evaluations

Subjective evaluations regarding ease of use and satisfaction were collected via questionnaires, and during debriefing at the conclusion of the session. The questionnaires utilized free-form responses and rating scales.

Scenario Completion Time (time on task)

The time to complete each scenario, not including subjective evaluation durations, was recorded.

Bibliography

1. Brooke, J. (1996). SUS: A "quick and dirty" usability scale. In P. W. Jordan, B. Thomas, B. A. Weerdmeester, & I. L. McClelland (Eds.), *Usability evaluation in industry* (pp. 189–194). London: Taylor & Francis.
2. After Scenario Questionnaire built from Lewis, J. R. (1995) *IBM Computer Usability Satisfaction Questionnaires: Psychometric Evaluation and Instructions for Use*. **International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction**, 7:1, 57-78. Retrieved from <https://garyperlman.com/quest/quest.cgi?form=ASQ>
3. Usability.gov. Planning a Usability Test. Retrieved from <https://www.usability.gov/how-to-and-tools/methods/planning-usability-testing.html>
4. Zazelenchuk, T. (2008): The Usability Data Logger V5.1.1. Retrieved from https://www.userfocus.co.uk/resources/datalogger_getlink.html